

INNOVATIVE SOLUTIONS FOR ONLINE PROJECTS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF MUSEUMS

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Annotation: *This article explains innovative solutions for online projects in the development of cultural tourism during the coronavirus pandemic based on the analysis of foreign and domestic museums. Opportunities for developing online tourism in the local tourism system of Uzbekistan were also highlighted.*

Keywords: *cultural tourism, Museum tourism, the pandemic, online projects, platform, hashtag, innovative solutions, Museum construction.*

Introduction

In the conditions of modern globalization, when the importance of universal values increases, the issue of popularization of material and spiritual monuments that are the basis of world civilization becomes relevant. Much attention is paid to the socio-cultural value of museums, their place in ensuring the interaction of society and culture. In this regard, the practice of processing museums around the world is rapidly developing as a popular and fast form of online delivery of information about their collections to the general public, a new, advanced method of museum marketing.

Materials and Methods

People will not travel abroad in public in the near future, prophecies that they will prefer domestic tourism have also become popular. Such thoughts were shared by an expert of the Spanish tourism industry, Fernando Gallardo, in an interview with RIA Novosti. "Tourist activity is currently in a critical state, the countries of Europe, China, Latin America have already closed their borders. A lot of people live in these regions, they do not go anywhere, and they will not travel in the near future," the expert said. In his opinion, the flow of tourists will "simply stop", in such a situation they cannot be distributed in one direction. This is an opinion that is said for a brief perspective. In the long term, economic shocks affect the global economy. In the conditions of economic depression, the tourism sector will need more time than usual to recover its strength, he stressed. According to the expert, China will be the first to get out of this situation, but the Chinese will not go to Europe, the United States, or the countries of Africa and Latin America, because there are other types of epidemics in those places, and the sanitary system is also not very good. "It will be domestic tourism," says Gallardo.

Although the quarantine does not completely stop the work of museums, museums are developing their activities online. Due to the coronavirus pandemic, remote services and online services are developing, as people do not leave their homes if possible. In particular, nowadays online museums have become popular among those who are interested in art and culture. The practical process of the communicative approach to the activities of museum tourism provides for the creation of an online exhibition environment taking into account existing conditions, the study, planning, organization of the museum's work and the use of modern technical means to attract an audience to the museum. The implementation of the project form is understood as a communicative approach to the work of the museum, the introduction of new systems into the work of the museum, the use of modern organizational methods of work, etc. In addition, another method of the communicative approach when designing museum activities online is the creation of a dramatic scenario for each museum equipment, exhibition and exhibit, as well as an attempt to reflect its specific history, feature, cultural significance and language.

During the coronavirus pandemic, various projects for the development of online tourism in museums around the world began to be implemented. The world-famous Hermitage in Russia on its Instagram page under the hashtag # izoizolyatsiya announced the #Hermitage and #hermitageathome campaign. According to the campaign, those who stayed at home due to the quarantine had to prepare compositions similar to compositions of famous works of art and post them on social networks. And the best creative reproductions were regularly shown on the St. Petersburg TV channel. It is worth noting that this action aroused great interest among thousands of people who were sitting at home in connection with the coronavirus pandemic. Currently, photos of hundreds of productions of copies of famous works of art are posted in the popular Isolation group, based on Facebook. They reflect the fantasies, humor and romantic mood of the participants. Well, giving a little freedom to the imagination, we will also play an important role in the development of online museum tourism when organizing such projects in the system of art museums of Uzbekistan. Unfortunately, the scientific staff of the museum is currently working rather poorly on updating the museum website, even when organizing online exhibitions.

The new virtual museums website, created by London-based developer Mac Grenfell, aims to include online museums where virtual travel is possible. You can view various museums in 3D format via a smartphone, laptop, tablet or computer, without leaving your home via the Internet system. In a nutshell, the website of virtual museums serves as a specific aggregator for searching and moving to online museums in the world. Based on the world map, museums with possible virtual access are allocated. You can click on one of the necessary territories, go to the museum's website and start a virtual tour at the same time.

Grenfell said that because the service is still new, not all museums have been included in it. But the site is constantly being updated, increasingly adding museums to its database. The best thing is that anyone who wants to use the virtual museums service can add a new museum. To do this, the Submit Museum button is placed on the site (add a museum). Here you will need to specify the name of the museum, as well as its website. If you register in the service, statistics of your visits and how long you have been in each museum are kept, but this is not necessary.

The development of museum communications online, the expansion of audience visits and, on this basis, the increase in its income are the basis of museum tourism. By their communicative function, museums not only have historical significance, but also serve the active participation of modern people in socio-cultural processes, ensuring harmony with society. The expansion of the range of museums' activities increases the demand for cultural and tourist resources and the possibility of employment not only for museum workers, but also for art managers, designers, artists, art historians.

Results

To this end, the first experiments in Uzbekistan began to be conducted in 2019. The Foundation for the Development of Culture and Art and Google Arts & Culture have agreed to publish a catalog of museum collections of Uzbekistan on the Internet. Google Arts & Culture is an online collection of 1,200 museums, galleries and exhibits from other organizations in 70 countries around the world. The Foundation for the Development of Culture and Art was one of the first in Uzbekistan to become a partner of this platform. Today, the foundation continues its project work online, and work on the collection is being completed to attract public attention to it.

One of the useful services provided by Google is Street View, which allows everyone to navigate through the streets of cities around the world without looking up from the computer screen. The creation of such projects at the crossroads of historical cities in the development of cultural tourism in Uzbekistan is considered one of the most important processes today. In this regard, the introduction of historical cities, which in recent years have become a distraction in the international arena, also plays an important role in online tourism. The development of functional architecture in the tourism infrastructure also creates new opportunities. Its basis is directly related to the development of tourism and innovation. In the practice of world museum work, the issues of the online museum of the historical urban environment also attract the attention of specialists. A number of controversial, unresolved issues remain within the framework of its problems until the end. "It is worth studying more deeply the experience of the international practice of restoration and functioning of the museum based on the urban environment by the methods of" in situ "and" ex situ " in Italy (Ferrara), Albania (Gjirokastra and Berat), Denmark (Aarhus), Bulgaria (Nessebar), Great Britain (the city department of the open-air museum in Bimisha) and Georgia (Tbilisi)." In addition to preserving the unique historical and cultural heritage, the audience is primarily focused on forming and

preserving the ideas of the residents of this city about the uniqueness of the environment.

In the XXI century, the protection of architectural heritage, the preservation of the historical environment of the city and the practice of its use in online tourism are one of the most promising areas. An important role is played by the online museum of architectural and artistic uniqueness of monuments and structures, which defines a historical city as a cultural phenomenon and forms a unique exposition based on an axiological approach. In cooperation with architects, historians, archaeologists, local residents, art historians, ethnographers and sociologists, it is now extremely important to focus on the museification of historical, cultural and social aspects of urban life. A special success of the work done in this area was the fact that the Republic of Uzbekistan was included in the Convention on the Protection of Universal Cultural and Natural Heritage. The Convention is the fundamental international legal document on the preservation of cultural and natural monuments. Each State that has signed the Convention acts on the basis of the general principles of preserving monuments of national and world significance existing on its territory. According to UNESCO, the Khiva "Ichan-kala" in 1990, the Bukhara Historical Center in 1993, the Shakhrisabz Historical Center in 2000, the Samarkand Cultural Center in 2001 were included in the list of World Heritage Sites. Since 2016, rapid actions on the construction of modern dwellings have led to the loss of the landscape of the territory on which the objects of cultural heritage of the Middle Ages are located. As a result, these historical centers remained under the threat of exclusion from the list. In addition, you can create important virtual tours and attract public attention by creating an online reconstruction of these historical centers and introducing them into cultural tourism.

The development of mobile navigation applications for historical objects provides convenience for tourists as a common database, such as identification of directions, modes of transport, distance size, addresses of shopping and catering establishments. In this regard, starting in 2018, under the leadership of the National Commission for UNESCO, under the auspices of foreign companies "Light Technology" and regional companies "Zyxel", practical developments were launched on the basis of a project called "mobile offers on cultural monuments of Uzbekistan". As part of the developments, virtual forms were also created, in which the solidarity of large central museums was ensured.

Today, there is also an online museum service in various social networks that writes reviews about the tourist potential of historical cities, that is, a modern PR-advertising system. For this purpose, there is a special platform on the tourist portal of tourist organizations around the world, where the personal pages of travelers are also viewed. In the development of cultural tourism, tourist portals are intended for their primary use at the stage of choosing a place to visit. Currently, at the stage of choosing the main goal, there is not only remote access of potential tourists to information about tourist routes

and services, but also an online access system. The travel portal tripadvisor constantly publishes statistics on its website, studying the online opinions of tourists in social networks. This portal provides a brief overview of the famous museums of Uzbekistan. The Uzbekistan Travel portal network plays an important role as a connecting link. In the first case, if the portal is a marketing tool for achieving a completely specific goal, then in the second case it manages users in many directions.

Among the mobile applications and platforms used in the practice of world museology, the MUSEUM mobile application is considered the most popular. It also systematizes views on the activities of museums in the social network. This system represents the top ten foreign museums based on the dynamics of audience visits and presents them in tabular form. This mobile application platform does not contain information about museums in Uzbekistan.

Conclusion

Today, in the era of the coronavirus pandemic, the State Department for Tourism Development is working to develop online tourism, support entrepreneurs and startups. The State Agency for Tourism Development is also developing a strategy for promoting the national product abroad together with the KHSTU and the National PR Center. According to him, at the end of the quarantine period, it is planned to organize a "Road-show " in Europe and the CIS countries. Work is underway to launch the site online-tourism.uz giving the opportunity to conduct virtual tours of tourism in Uzbekistan. This will be the first platform offering virtual travel throughout Uzbekistan. Currently, in a difficult period associated with quarantine, the promotion of tourism in Uzbekistan is the most necessary. This allows tourists to plan their trip in advance without leaving home. In this regard, the chairman of the State Agency for Tourism Development A. Abdukhakimov expressed the following thoughts on the committee's website – " Today, cooperation has begun with museums and other tourist facilities to launch virtual tours. Taking this opportunity, we will attract talented specialists working in this direction to cooperate, with whom you can conduct online activities. At the same time, we urge the owners of cafes, restaurants and other tourist facilities to take the necessary measures to ensure virtual travel, which will allow these tourists to choose places that suit their taste and that suit them from now on." After the end of the quarantine period associated with the coronavirus in Uzbekistan, it is planned to subsidize start-up projects in the field of tourism, including innovative business ideas, especially programs aimed at creating amenities for young people and tourists. The development of multimedia projects in the context of various museums in the innovative information sphere in the development of cultural tourism in Uzbekistan is considered as one of the promising tasks. In this regard, the organization of virtual tours, the development of advertising on international travel portals and sites create an opportunity to harmonize with modern principles.

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